

MUSEUM. I. SAVITSKY - THE LOUVRE IN THE SANDS**Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnadbek ugli**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16602192>**Introduction.**

The Republic of Karakalpakstan and its capital Nukus are the most extraordinary tourist destinations in the world. This is the definition of the world-readable British newspaper The Telegraph, which included the Louvre in the Sands in the "top ten" of 2015, under the second number. And the authors of the "Leisure" column in the Sunday supplement, no less readable by The New York Times and the International Herald Tribune, in the summer of 2009 advised art-savvy readers to visit the Nukus Museum "must-see-before-I-die destination", and called this unique museum, popularly referred to as the Savitsky Museum or simply the Nukus Museum - the Louvre in the Sands.

The State Museum of Arts named after I.V. Savitsky (abbreviated as Karakalpak State Museum of Arts, Nukus Art Museum) (Uzbek Savitskiy nomidagi Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi Davlat San'at Muzeyi) is one of the largest museums in Uzbekistan. The museum's collection is recognized as the second in the world in terms of significance and volume among the collections of works of the Russian avant-garde, as well as the best art collection in the Asian region.

The museum was founded in 1966 by a remarkable scientist, ethnographer and artist and collector Igor Savitsky. The history of the creation and development of the museum is unique, just like its collection. The collection of the State Museum of Arts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I. V. Savitsky was assembled in an unprecedentedly short time. In just a few years, Savitsky managed to collect in the museum one of the most complete collections of fine art of the Russian and Turkestan avant-garde, one of the most significant collections of decorative and applied art of Karakalpakia and a unique collection of archaeological exhibits of Ancient Khorezm. This fact has no analogue in the

practice of world museum collecting. After the death of I.V. Savitsky in 1984, his name was given to the museum. Since 1991, the museum has been awarded the first international category, which puts the museum on a par with the Tretyakov Gallery, the Russian Museum and the Hermitage.

The modern collection of the museum contains more than 90,000 different exhibits. Museum collections are stored and exhibited in 3 buildings with a total area of almost 7 thousand square meters. There are 6 departments in the museum: Department of Fine Arts; Department of Archeology; Mass Education Department; Department of Folk Applied Arts; Restoration Department, as well as the Accounting and Storage Sector.

The collection of Russian avant-garde paintings of the 20-40s of the 20th century, the second largest in the world after the collection of the Russian Museum in St. Petersburg, brought world fame to the Nukus Museum.

“Many of the authors whose works are presented in our halls (Robert Falk, Kliment Redko, Lyubov Popova, sculptors Vera Mukhina and Sarah Lebedeva) were well known in Europe, — The museum exhibits genuine masterpieces by the artist A. Volkov and the finest stylist Usto Mumin (A. Nikolaev), famous impressionist artists who lived in Uzbekistan - P. Benkov and Z. Kovalevskaya, early works by U. Tansykbaev and N. Karakhan, close in spirit and style to the avant-garde, magnificent paintings by V. Rozhdestvensky, E. Korovai , M. Kurzina, N. Shevchenko. The art collection is adorned with works by Russian artists of the early 20th century P. Kuznetsov, A. Kuprin, N. Ulyanov. The museum acquaints the audience with the works of contemporary artists of Karakalpakstan - Zh. Izentaev, B. Serikeev, R. Matevosyan, Zh. Kuttymuradov.

The collection of Karakalpak folk arts and crafts includes about 70 thousand exhibits, including pile carpets, patterned weaving, embroidery, applique, embossing and embroidery on leather, carving and inlay on wood, jewelry, metal products, handmade fabrics. The museum exhibits works of ancient and medieval art of the peoples who inhabited this region, as well as objects that tell about the trade and cultural relations of the Khorezmians with the East and West. Zoroastrian terracotta figurines of Anahita - the goddess of fertility, ossuaries - vessels for the burial of the remains of the deceased ancestors of fire worshipers with images of lions, female and male heads, in the form of mausoleums - are the most ancient exhibits of the museum.

Late antiquity of the 1st-4th centuries includes a bronze pin in the shape of a hand holding an apple, a silver ring with a carnelian seal depicting a dolphin, and a terracotta figurine of a woman with a vine. Bronze lamps and a collection of

ceramics - khums for storing grain, jugs and other items decorated with relief ornaments date back to the 12th-13th centuries. The department of decorative and applied arts of Karakalpakstan exhibits works, most of which belong to the second half of the 19th - early 20th centuries. Among them are objects made of wood and leather, which were used by nomadic peoples on campaigns - saddles decorated with silver, cases for dishes, mortars for tobacco, carved doors for a yurt. Of particular interest are carpet products for the decoration of Karakalpak yurts - patterned strips "beldeu" and "ak-bastur", for the creation of which a unique technique of relief pile weaving is used. Hands of nameless folk craftsmen embroidered with silk, beads and pearls "saukele" - wedding headdresses, national costumes, miniature tea bags. And, of course, the richest collection of ancient Karakalpak silver jewelry with inserts of carnelian and turquoise will not leave anyone indifferent.

Samples of collections and exhibits of the museum:

To date, the Museum of Arts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after I. V. Savitsky is the most visited tourist attraction in the republic. About 70,000 people visit the museum every year, of which more than 3,000 are foreigners, and the main purpose of their visit is the museum.

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